

RELIGION AND PURIFICATION OF SOUL

RELIGION Y PURIFICACION DEL ALMA

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ABSTRACT

The Jainism emphasizes three major teachings about the purification of the soul (jiva), Ahimsa, Aparigraha and anekantwad. Jainism, The focus of this religion has been purification of the soul by means of right conduct, right faith and right knowledge. The ultimate goal of Hinduism is Moksha or liberation (total freedom). In Hinduism, purification of the soul is a goal that one must work to attain. The Buddhism is the science of pursuing the aim of making the human mind perfect, and of purifying the human soul. The knowledge of purifying of the soul and softening of the hearts is as essential for human. They having the correct motivations means purifying our souls from hypocrisy, caprice, and heedlessness. The primary goal of Taoism may be described as the mystical intuition of the Tao, which is the way, the undivided unity, and the ultimate Reality. According to the Christianity access to truth cannot be conceived without purity of the soul.

Keyword: Human, Religion, Freedom, Practice.

RESUMEN

Presenta una comparación de los conceptos de purificación del alma entre el Jainism, el Budismo, el Hinduismo, el Taoismo y el Cristianismo. Coinciden en búsqueda de la correcta purificación del alma en asuntos como la hipocresía. Estos procesos de purificación del alma se presentan como esenciales para el hombre

Palabras clave: Humano, Religión, Libertad, Práctica.

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INTRODUCTION

Man is a being in three parts, composed of the spirit, the carnal soul and the body, each needing to be satisfied. These three components are so interrelated with one another, and their needs are so different that neglecting one result in man's failing to attain 'perfection' [1]. The knowledge of purifying of the soul and softening of the hearts is as essential for human such as water for the fish, or air for the rest of the living creatures [2].

Allah has borne man into a struggle of good and evil by creating within him both righteous and evil desires. Examples of good desires are to become an obedient servant of Allah and to work righteously, likewise, an example of evil desires is the endless pursuit of worldly status and self-satisfaction, which are only indications of greed and arrogance that breed more of the same. Allah wishes man to develop his righteous characteristics and hence purify his nafs by eliminating his evil desires. Two words that mean to cleanse are tasfia and tazkia. The root word of tasfia is safa – "to clean," whereas tazkia comes from the Arabic verb meaning "to purify." A mirror that has accumulated a layer of dust has only to be wiped with a dust cloth and some polish to sparkle like new and it will be cleaned. The dust is only superficial and hence

easily wiped away: this is an example of tasfia The word falah is so potent that it has been connected to only three major actions in the Holy Quran. The first of these is tauba, or repentance. The second action to attain this honor is tazkia, and the third of these is salat (prayer). [3] Every major religious tradition has its mystical element, often described by a distinctive term representing a distinct tradition with that religion. Thus, in Islam, it is called tasawwuf or Sufism; in Judaism it is called Kabbalah. In Christianity it is often referred simply as Christian mysticism. In Hinduism, the mystical schools are extremely many, but the more popular ones include Raja Yoga and Vedanta. These teachings are often identified with the name of the teacher, such as Ramana Maharshi, J. Krishnamurti, etc. Buddhism also has diverse mystical traditions, such as Tibetan Buddhism and Zen Buddhism. The purification of the soul is the growth process after the spiritual consciousness has begun to be active in one's life. Like the preceding stages, there are sub stages and facets to this. Modern transpersonal psychology and psychiatry have identified various conditions that arrest the growth process in one's spiritual life. Classic mystical literature, both eastern and western, is replete with guidelines on this phase. St. John of the Cross-wrote of the "dark nights" of the soul and the senses, Buddhism speaks of the ten fetters that must be overcome until one has become a full arhat. The spiritual initiations in theosophical literature speak of these same fetters [4].

DISCUSSION

The Purification of the soul in Jainism

According to the Jaina's religious perfection and purification of the soul could occur only when the soul is in a state of eternal liberation from and non-attachment to corporeal (material) bodies. Liberation of the soul is impeded by the accumulation of karmans, bits of material, generated by a person's actions, that bind themselves to the soul and consequently bind the soul to material bodies through many births; this has the effect of thwarting the full self-realization and freedom of the soul [5].

The Jainism emphasizes three major teachings about the purification of the soul (jiva). Ahimsa teaches that all life in all forms is valuable and therefore should not be destroyed or injured. Recognized as a virtually impossible ideal for humans, ahimsa also teaches that although human life is inevitably destructive, its ultimate aim is to cause as little harm as possible to other creatures, including other persons. Ahimsa extends to thinking and speaking as well because abusive words and negative thoughts can harm others. Jain would not agree with the well-worn ditty Sticks and stones may break my bones but words will never hurt me. Aparigrapha teaches that through non-attachment to both things and people, one kindles the way to inner peace. It is notable that Jainism teaches that this non-acquisitiveness is not only the way to inner liberation, but is also valuable for the world as

well. Jainism teaches that if more people limit their needs and desires, then fewer demands will be placed on the environment. The third great teaching of Jainism is anekantwad, relativity loosely translated. This teaches that it is important to avoid polarized issues and judgmentalism. In other words, anekantwad instructs followers to cultivate open-mindedness, and to be sensitive to the truth that the issues can be seen from many different angles. Because truth has many facets, the enlightened person is responsive to the subtleties of existence [6]. Jainism, The focus of this religion has been purification of the soul by means of right conduct, right faith and right knowledge [7].

The Purification of the soul in Hinduism

The ultimate goal of Hinduism is Moksha or liberation (total freedom). The path for Saivism divides the spiritual progress of the soul into four progressive stages of belief and practice, called Chariya, Kriya, Yoga, and Jnana. The soul evolves through the process of reincarnation, gradually maturing from the instinctive intellectual sphere into virtuous and moral living. It then progresses into temple worship and devotion, followed by internalized meditation, yoga, and its disciplines. The Karma is the law of cause and effect by which each individual creates his own destiny by his thoughts, words, and deeds. The soul reincarnates, evolving through many births until all karma has been resolved. Divine beings exist in unseen inner worlds and temple worship rituals and sacraments, as well as personal devotions, create a

communion with the gods (Devas) and Gods. A spiritually awakened master (Sat Guru) is essential to know the transcendent absolute, as are individual discipline, good conduct, purification, self-inquiry, and meditation. All life is sacred and to be loved and revered, in the practice of nonviolence (Ahimsa). No particular religion teaches the only way to salvation above all others, but all genuine religious paths are facets [8].

In Hinduism, “the Yogi works for purification of the soul: he throws off selfish attachment.” A wise Hindu seeks purification by not being bound by wants. In Hinduism, purification of the soul is a goal that one must work to attain. Millions of Hindus resort to ritual purification washing in the Ganges River is a popular type of purification where occasionally millions of Hindus will wash in the river at certain auspicious times [9].

The Purification of the soul in Buddhism

Buddhism is a philosophy based on the teachings of Lord Buddha (563 BCE-483 BCE), who was born as Siddhartha Gautama, a Shakya prince in Lumbini, Nepal. The teachings preached by Lord Buddha subsequently turned into a religion, known as Buddhism. The core of Buddhism lies in the purification of mind and soul by realizing the truth and getting rid of the worldly desires. Basically, it was the principles of

Karma in the doctrine of Buddhism that made the religion one of the major ones in the world [10].

The Buddha is a teacher on purification of mind, and because such purification is so integral a part of his Teaching, he has expounded a great number of suttas dealing with the subject. The most important of these suttas from the Pali Canon are available in translation in WHEEL editions. Each of these works presents the words of the Buddha with practical advice on how to proceed with the work of inward purification and how to deal with the problems that arise in the course of practice [11]. The Buddhism is the science of pursuing the aim of making the human mind perfect, and of purifying the human soul. Only by purifying one's soul, language and body would he be able to reach enlightenment and the state of Bodhisatva. The essence of Buddhist teaching lies in helping human beings reach this state, and developing his own inner and outer ability [12].

The Purification of the soul in Islam

Islam is the religion of truth. It is the embodiment of the code of life, which God, the Creator and Lord of the universe, has revealed for the guidance of mankind. For the proper development of human life, man needs two elements: (a) the resources to maintain life and to fulfill the material needs of the individual and society, and (b) knowledge of the principles of individual and social behavior to enable man to fulfill

himself and to maintain justice and tranquility in human life. The Lord of the universe has provided for both of these in full measure. To cater to the material needs of man, He has put all of nature's resources at his disposal. [13] Among the missions of the Prophet, Allah sent him with the command to purify the souls of mankind. In addition the Prophet, was sent with three tasks: 1) To teach the Qur'aan. 2) To teach the Sunnah. 3) To show the means of purifying the soul.

This purification is obtained by doing the proper acts of worship and by avoiding sins and disobedience [14]. The having the correct motivations means purifying our souls from hypocrisy, caprice, heedlessness, and everything else that keeps us from serving Allah for His sake alone. This purification of the soul is called tazkiyah [15].

It should be pointed out that only a soul, which has been purified could bring benefit to mankind through the sciences. Otherwise, as witnessed in the last phase of human history, science and technology can be so deadly to mankind that millions of people lose their lives, and other millions of them are left homeless as orphans and widows. Only when purified souls are endowed with sciences and enabled to employ them, does this lead to true felicity and salvation for mankind [16].

The Purification of the soul in Taoist

The primary goal of Taoism may be described as the mystical

intuition of the Tao, which is the way, the undivided unity, and the ultimate Reality. The Taoist observes "wu-wei" or non-doing, like water, which without effort seeks and finds its proper level. This path includes purifying oneself by stilling appetites and emotions. This is accomplished in part through meditation, breath control, and other forms of inner discipline, generally under a master. The foremost practice is goodness or naturalness, and detachment from the worldly things. [17] The ultimate goal of taoist is freedom from desire. A Taoist is to do the opposite refrain from working towards the goal. The reason that the sage is to refrain from actions is that he must truly be free from desire and not work to convince him that he is free. [18]

The Purification of the soul in Christianity

The Access to truth cannot be conceived of without purity of the soul. Purity of the soul is the consequence of self-knowledge and a condition for understanding the text [19].

Baptism is a rite of purification by water, a ceremony invoking the grace of God to regenerate the person, free him or her from sin, and make that person a part of the church. Formal baptism is performed by immersion pouring, or sprinkling depending on the tradition. Baptism can be performed on babies or postponed until the person is relatively mature and can make a formal confession that Jesus Christ is Lord and Savior of his or her life. Partaking of the elements, the bread and wine

(grape juice in some traditions), the believer is united in some form with Christ and with other members. Much difference of opinion exists with the celebration of the Lord's Supper. Some believe that a change occurs by which the body and blood of Christ join with the bread and wine; others believe that no such change takes place, but that there is a union with Christ and each other; still others believe it is an occasion to remember the death and resurrection of Christ. Some Protestants use unleavened bread others use raised bread. Some use wine others also use unfermented grape juice. All Protestants receive both elements. The frequency of celebrating the Lord's Supper ranges from weekly to once a year. At Bureau facilities, communion should be provided once a month at a minimum [20].

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